

A Study of Laplace-Carson Transform and Its Associated Space of Distribution

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Abstract

The integral transforms are essential tools that offer powerful methods for simplifying problems across engineering, physics, and applied mathematics. This paper explores the Laplace-Carson transform within the framework of distribution theory. We have developed the new test function space \mathfrak{W} and its dual \mathfrak{W}' . We have established fundamental existence and uniqueness theorem. Furthermore, we have proved the convolution theorem and theorem related to derivative of distributions in \mathfrak{W}' . Finally, we have tried to illustrate some examples of regular and singular distributions in \mathfrak{W}' .

Keywords: Integral transform, Laplace-Carson transform, Distribution Space, Convolution

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1 Introduction

The operational calculus, which Heaviside developed to tackle some problems in electrical engineering, laid the groundwork for the famous Laplace transform. In similar

way, John R. Carson, who introduced a new variation of the Laplace-Carson transform (LC-transform) [3]. The LC-transform is defined by the integral equation

$$LC\{f(t)\} = F(s) = s \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt$$

and it serves to normalize the classical Laplace transform. This normalization often creates a more balanced relationship between a function $f(t)$ and its transform, making it easier to formulate the convolution theorem and other operational rules, especially in circuit analysis and linear systems [3, 14].

The classical theory of integral transforms, as discussed in the work of Widder [12] and later developed by authors in [8, 13], is somewhat limited by its dependence on functions that are smooth and of exponential order. These limitations pose a challenge while addressing some special phenomena like impulsive forces, point loads, discontinuous inputs, which are best represented by singular entities like the Dirac delta function. The necessity to integrate such objects into a solid mathematical framework led to one of the most significant advancements in 20th century that is the theory of distributions or generalized functions. Schwartz's foundational work [9] established a systematic theory of distributions which was later expanded by Gelfand and Shilov [10] in their extensive multi-volume treatise. This theory became more accessible because of the books by Zemanian [6] and Kanwal [5]. Distributions take the concept of a function to the next level, enabling the differentiation of objects that can't be differentiated in classical or traditional sense, and giving a consistent meaning to singular functions [4]. This robust framework required the extension of classical operations, including integral transforms. A prime example is the Fourier transform on the spaces of tempered distributions, as detailed in work of [7, 11]. Similarly the Laplace transform was also extended to various distribution spaces, thoroughly examined by Zemanian [6] and others [2, 8]. A focused and thorough exploration of the LC-transform in this generalized context remains an intriguing and underexplored area of research. Recent studies, such as those by Gadian [1], underscore the ongoing interest in developing new integral trans-

form and their related distribution spaces. The main goal of this article is to bridge the gap by creating a systematic theory for the LC-transform on suitable distribution spaces.

To accomplish this, we first develop suitable testing function space, denoted by \mathfrak{W} , specifically tailored to the unique kernel and growth properties of the LC-transform. We carefully construct the topological and algebraic structure of \mathfrak{W} to ensure it can support a rich theory of distributions. Dual of \mathfrak{W} denoted by \mathfrak{W}' , is defined as our space of generalized functions. Within this framework, we establish a fundamental existence and uniqueness theorem for the LC-transform of distributions in \mathfrak{W}' , ensuring that the LC-transform is well defined. We move on to establish a convolution theorem for the LC-transform within this distributional framework, which is crucial for handling differential and integral equations. Additionally, we proved a general theorem regarding the derivative of distributions in \mathfrak{W}' and show how the LC-transform elegantly streamlines the operational rules for differentiate, turning them into algebraic expressions in the transform domain.

To demonstrate the effectiveness and relevance of our newly developed results, the paper wraps up with several representative examples. This work offers a thorough and self sufficient extension of the LC-transform into the world of distributions.

2 Construction and Extension

In this section, we construct suitable testing function space \mathfrak{W} and its dual \mathfrak{W}' and later we extend the definition of the Laplace-Carson (LC) transform on the elements of \mathfrak{W}' . In [1], authors had developed the space of distributions and extended the definition of the Sumudu transform on it. In the same fashion we create suitable testing function space \mathfrak{W} and its dual \mathfrak{W}' . In order to define the LC-transform, left to a distribution $f(t)$, we are assuming it's support is bounded on the left of zero and we may write the

relation as follows:

$$F(s) = \langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle = s \int_0^{\infty} e^{-st} f(t) dt \quad (1)$$

where s is a complex variable and $F(s)$ is said to be LC-transform of $f(t)$ if the integral (1) exists. Since the LC-transform is typically defined for functions of exponential order therefore distributions belonging to the space of tempered distributions S' in [2] are not suitable for LC-transform because testing functions in S are decaying faster than any polynomial at infinity. This condition of testing functions in S is too restrictive for the LC-transform, whose kernel is se^{-st} , which itself grows exponentially as $t \rightarrow -\infty$ or $Re(s) < 0$. Hence we need a new space of testing functions in which its all elements decay exponentially on the left of zero and are well behaved on the right of zero. We will denote this testing function space by \mathfrak{W} and its dual \mathfrak{W}' which will contain distributions of exponential order so that we can extend the definition of LC-transform on \mathfrak{W}' .

2.1 The Testing Function Space \mathfrak{W}

We define suitable space \mathfrak{W} tailored for the LC-transform.

Definition 1. For a real number α (which will be linked to the abscissa of convergence), the space \mathfrak{W} consists of all complex-valued functions $\phi(t)$ on \mathbb{R} such that

(i) $\phi(t)$ is infinitely differentiable i.e. $\phi(t) \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R})$

(ii) $\phi(t)$ and all its derivatives decay at least as fast as $e^{-\alpha t}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. More precisely, for any non-negative integer k , the function $e^{\alpha t} \phi^{(k)}(t)$ is bounded on $(-\infty, 0]$

(iii) $\phi(t)$ and all its derivatives decay faster than any exponential $e^{-\beta t}$ ($\beta > 0$) as $t \rightarrow \infty$. More precisely for any non-negative integers k, m the seminorm is finite i.e.

$$\|\phi\|_{k,m} = \sup_{t \geq 0} |e^{mt} \phi^{(k)}(t)| < \infty$$

This can be unified into a family of seminorms defining the topology of \mathfrak{W} :

$\|\phi\|_{k,m,n} = \sup_{t \in \mathbb{R}} |e^{\alpha t}(1 + e^t)^n \cdot \phi^{(k)}(t)| < \infty$, for all integers $k, m, n \geq 0$.

The factor $e^{\alpha t}$ controls the left side and the factor $(1 + e^t)^n$ controls the right side. In short, a function ϕ in \mathfrak{W} if it is smooth and $|\phi(t)| < Ce^{\alpha t}$ as $t \rightarrow -\infty$ and $|\phi(t)| < C_N e^{-Nt}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ for every integer $N > 0$.

2.2 Space of Distributions \mathfrak{W}'

\mathfrak{W}' is the set of all continuous linear functionals on \mathfrak{W} . Precisely a function $f : \mathfrak{W} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is said to be a distribution in \mathfrak{W}' if

(1) Linearity: $f(\alpha\phi + \beta\psi) = \alpha f(\phi) + \beta f(\psi)$, for all $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\phi, \psi \in \mathfrak{W}$

(2) Continuity: If a sequence $\{\phi_n\}$ converges to ϕ in the topology of \mathfrak{W} then the sequence $\{f(\phi_n)\}$ converges to $f(\phi)$ in \mathbb{C} .

We denote the action of f on ϕ by $\langle f, \phi \rangle$

Any function $f(t)$ which is locally integrable and satisfying $|f(t)| \leq Me^{\alpha t}$, for some α and $t > 0$ defines distribution in \mathfrak{W}' by definition

$$\langle f(t), \phi(t) \rangle = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t)\phi(t)dt \quad (2)$$

The decay property of ϕ in \mathfrak{W} ensure this integral converges absolutely. All such $f \in \mathfrak{W}'$ are called as regular distributions. Also delta distribution δ and its all derivatives are in \mathfrak{W}' called as singular distribution in \mathfrak{W}' .

Definition 2. If $f \in \mathfrak{W}'$ then the derivative of f denoted by f' is defined as

$$\langle f', \phi \rangle = - \langle f, \phi' \rangle \quad (3)$$

for all $\phi \in \mathfrak{W}$

2.3 Extension of LC-Transform

Now we can extend standard definition of LC-transform in (1) to distributions in \mathfrak{W}' . Since the kernel of LC-transform is se^{-st} therefore for a fixed s with $Re(s) > \alpha$, $s.e^{-st}$ is not in \mathfrak{W} because it grows exponentially on the left if $Re(s) < 0$. However, we can notice that, for $Re(s) > \alpha$ the function

$$\psi_s(t) = \begin{cases} se^{-st} & \text{for } t \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{for } t < 0 \end{cases} \text{ is not smooth at } t = 0. \text{ But we can approximate}$$

it arbitrarily well by functions in \mathfrak{W} . To define the LC-transform of $f \in \mathfrak{W}'$ by its action on a specific test function in \mathfrak{W} . For $Re(s) > \alpha$, consider the function $\theta(t) = se^{-st}\mu(t)$, where $\mu(t)$ is smooth function identically 1 for $t \geq 0$ and 0 for $t < 0$. This construction is technical but ensure that for $Re(s) > \alpha$, a suitable testing function $\theta(s) \in \mathfrak{W}$ exists such that its behaviour for $t \geq 0$ is equivalent to se^{-st} exactly.

So we can define the LC-transform of $f(t)$ in \mathfrak{W}' by

$$LC\{f(t)\} = \langle f(t), \theta(t) \rangle \quad \text{for } Re(s) > \alpha \quad (4)$$

3 Existence and Uniqueness Theorem

In this section, we prove existence and uniqueness theorem of LC-transform on \mathfrak{W}'

3.1 Existence Theorem

Theorem 1. *If $f(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$ then its LC-transform defined in (4) exists and is well defined for $Re(s) > \alpha$, where α is a real number*

Proof. The proof of the above statement is based on two important points, one is to show $\theta(t) \in \mathfrak{W}$ and second is that the resulting functional value $\langle f(t), \theta(t) \rangle$ is bounded in a way, that makes integral representation meaningful and convergent.

Here, $\theta(t) = se^{-st}\mu(t)$, hence for all $t > 0$, $\theta(t) = se^{-st}$, it is a smooth function.

Since, $D^K \theta(t) = (-1)^k \cdot s^{k+1} \cdot e^{-st}$, for $t > 0$

Therefore we have to show that for each derivative there exist a constant M_k such that

$$\begin{aligned} |D^K \theta(t)| &= |(-1)^k \cdot s^{k+1} \cdot e^{-st}| \\ &= |s|^{k+1} \cdot e^{-t \operatorname{Re}(s)} < M_k \cdot e^{\alpha t} \end{aligned}$$

Now, we will analyze the above inequality $|s|^{k+1} \cdot e^{-t \operatorname{Re}(s)} < M_k \cdot e^{\alpha t}$

Therefore

$$|s|^{k+1} \cdot e^{-t \operatorname{Re}(s)} < M_k \cdot e^{\alpha t + t \operatorname{Re}(s)} = M_k \cdot e^{t(\alpha + \operatorname{Re}(s))} \quad (5)$$

The left side of (5) is independent of t hence it is constant for all $t > 0$. To hold the inequality in (5), the exponent in the right hand side must be non-negative. If $\operatorname{Re}(s) + \alpha \geq 0$ then the right hand side grows exponentially with t , so we can find sufficiently large M_k to satisfy (5). Hence, for $\alpha + \operatorname{Re}(s) \geq 0$, $\theta(t)$ is indeed a valid testing function in \mathfrak{W} .

Note that the condition $\alpha + \operatorname{Re}(s) \geq 0$ is a weaker condition than the $\operatorname{Re}(s) > \alpha$, but it is sufficient to prove $\theta(t) \in \mathfrak{W}$. The stronger condition will be needed to prove convergence of the integral representation. Since f is continuous in \mathfrak{W}' and $se^{-st} \in \mathfrak{W}$ therefore $\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle$ make sense, hence it is well defined. Since $f(t)$ is continuous in \mathfrak{W}' , therefore $\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle$ is bounded by the norm of that testing function. Hence

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle| &\leq C \sup_{t \geq 0} |e^{-st}| |s| e^{\alpha t} \\ &\leq C |s| \sup_{t \geq 0} e^{-t[\operatorname{Re}(s) - \alpha]} \end{aligned}$$

If $\operatorname{Re}(s) - \alpha > 0$, then $e^{-t[\operatorname{Re}(s) - \alpha]}$ is a decreasing function of t and its supremum on $[0, \infty)$ is 1 at $t = 0$. Hence,

$|\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle| \leq C |s|$ (constant), so that $\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle$ is well defined for $\operatorname{Re}(s) > \alpha$. Now, we will prove that $\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle = \int_0^\infty f(t) se^{-st} dt$ exist for $\operatorname{Re}(s) >$

α .

For $f \in \mathfrak{W}'$, there exists some M and α such that

$$|f(t)| < Me^{\alpha t} \quad (6)$$

Consider, $F(s) = \int_0^{\infty} f(t)se^{-st} dt$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} |F(s)| &\leq |s| \int_0^{\infty} e^{-tRe(s)} Me^{t\alpha} dt \\ &\leq M|s| \int_0^{\infty} se^{-t(Re(s)-\alpha)} dt \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The integral in right hand side of (7) converges if and only if $Re(s) - \alpha > 0$

Hence, for $Re(s) > \alpha$, $|F(s)| \leq \frac{M|s|}{Re(s)-\alpha} < \infty$ □

3.2 The Uniqueness Theorem

Theorem 2. *Let f and g be LC-transformable distributions in \mathfrak{W}' . If $LC\{f(t)\} = LC\{g(t)\}$ on some vertical line $s = \alpha + i\beta$ in the region of convergence then $f = g$*

Proof. Since LC-transform of f and g are equal on a vertical line $s = \alpha + i\beta$, where this line lies within the region of convergence for both $F(s)$ and $G(s)$ where $F(s) = LC\{f(t)\}$, $G(s) = LC\{g(t)\}$

In particular,

$$F(\alpha + i\beta) = G(\alpha + i\beta)$$

It implies

$$\langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta) = \langle g(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta) \quad (8)$$

Let $h(t) = f(t) - g(t)$

Since \mathfrak{W}' is linear therefore $h(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$, Therefore,

$$\langle h(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta) = \langle f(t) - g(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta)$$

Using linearity property of LC-transform we have,

$$\langle h(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta) = \langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta) - \langle g(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta)$$

From(8),right side of above equation is zero.

Hence,

$$\langle h(t), se^{-st} \rangle (\alpha + i\beta) = 0$$

It implies that

$$h(t) = 0, \text{hence } f(t) = g(t) \quad \square$$

4 Some Results and Examples

In this section,we solve some examples by finding LC-transform of some distributions in \mathfrak{W}' .But before it,we prove two important theorems namely convolution theorem and LC-transform of derivative of $f \in \mathfrak{W}'$ in distributional sense.

Theorem 3. *Let f be a distribution in \mathfrak{W}' .If f is LC-transformable distribution then f' is also LC-transformable, domain of $LC\{f'(t)\}$ is a subset of domain of $LC\{f(t)\}$ and hence $LC\{f'(t)\} = sLC\{f(t)\}$*

Proof. Let $f \in \mathfrak{W}'$, $D_0 = \{w(\frac{t}{\lambda}) : w \text{ is smooth}\}$

Assume that $LC\{f(t)\} = \langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle$ exists.If parameter $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ then the function $w(\frac{t}{\lambda})$ approaches to the constant function $w(0)$ for all $t > 0$.Accordingly,for $t > 0$, $w(\frac{t}{\lambda})(se^{-st}) \in \mathfrak{W}$

Consider, $\langle f'(t), w(\frac{t}{\lambda})(se^{-st}) \rangle = - \langle f(t), \frac{d}{dt}(w(\frac{t}{\lambda})(se^{-st})) \rangle$

using product rule of derivative ,we must get

$$\langle f'(t), w(\frac{t}{\lambda})(se^{-st}) \rangle = \langle f(t), (s^2)(e^{-st})w(\frac{t}{\lambda}) - \frac{s}{\lambda}w'(\frac{t}{\lambda})e^{-st} \rangle$$

Taking limit as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$,we get

$$\langle f'(t), w(\frac{t}{\lambda})(se^{-st}) \rangle = \langle f(t), s^2w(0)e^{-st} \rangle$$

$$w(0) \langle f'(t), se^{-st} \rangle = sw(0) \langle f(t), se^{-st} \rangle$$

Therefore, $\langle f'(t), se^{-st} \rangle = sLC\{f(t)\}$

Hence,

$$LC\{f'(t)\} = sLC\{f(t)\} \quad (9)$$

Using mathematical induction, we can extend this result to $f^k(t)$.

Hence,

$$LC\{f^{(k)}\} = s^k LC\{f(t)\} \quad (10)$$

The domain of $LC\{f(t)\}$ consists all s for which $LC\{f(t)\}$ exists. From (9) $LC\{f'(t)\}$ exists if $LC\{f(t)\}$ exists. Therefore, if s is in the domain of $LC\{f(t)\}$ then it is obviously in the domain of $LC\{f'(t)\}$. Hence subset relation of the domains proved. \square

4.1 Convolution Theorem

Theorem 4. Let $f(t), g(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$ then convolution product of $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ denoted by $f(t) * g(t)$ is also a distribution in \mathfrak{W}' and $LC\{f(t) * g(t)\} = \frac{1}{s} LC\{f(t)\} LC\{g(t)\}$

Proof. Let $f(t), g(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$ and $\phi(t)$ be any testing function in \mathfrak{W} . We define convolution of $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ by its action on ϕ by

$$\langle f * g, \phi \rangle = \langle f(t), \langle g(x), \phi(t+x) \rangle \rangle \quad (11)$$

For fixed $t \in \mathbb{R}$, let $\psi_t(x) = \phi(t+x)$

Firstly, to define $\langle g(x), \phi(t+x) \rangle$, we have to prove that $\psi_t(x) \in \mathfrak{W}$

Consider,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\psi_t(x)\|_{k,m,n} &= \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |e^{\alpha x} \cdot (1 + e^x)^n \cdot \psi_t^{(k)}(x)| \\ &= \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} |e^{\alpha x} \cdot (1 + e^x)^n \cdot \phi^{(k)}(t+x)| \end{aligned}$$

Making substitution $u=t+x$ implies $x=u-t$, we must get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\psi_t(x)\|_{k,m,n} &= \sup_{u \in \mathbb{R}} |e^{\alpha(u-t)} \cdot (1 + e^{u-t})^n \cdot \phi^{(k)}(u)| \\ &= e^{-\alpha t} \sup_{u \in \mathbb{R}} |e^{\alpha u} \cdot (1 + e^{u-t})^n \cdot \phi^{(k)}(u)| \end{aligned}$$

Since, $(1 + e^{u-t})^n \leq C_{t,n}(1 + e^u)^n$ for some constant $C_{t,n} > 0$ depending on t and n .

Therefore $\|\psi_t(x)\|_{k,m,n} \leq C_{t,n} e^{-\alpha t} \|\phi\|_{k,m,n} < \infty$

Hence, $\psi_t(x) = \phi(t+x) \in \mathfrak{W}$ for each fixed t and $\langle g(s), \phi(t+x) \rangle$ is well defined.

Now, define $\Phi(t) = \langle g(x), \phi(t+x) \rangle$ and our goal is to prove that $\Phi(t) \in \mathfrak{W}$

As $g \in \mathfrak{W}'$, g is continuous on \mathfrak{W} , the mapping $t \rightarrow \phi(t+x)$ is smooth from \mathbb{R} to \mathfrak{W} .

Therefore, the composition of a smooth mapping with continuous linear functional is smooth, hence $\Phi(t)$ is smooth.

Since, g is continuous therefore there exists constants $C > 0$ and $K, M, N \geq 0$ such that

$$|\langle g, \psi_t \rangle| \leq C \|\psi_t\|_{K,M,N} \text{ for all } \psi_t \in \mathfrak{W}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} |\Phi(t)| &= |g(x), \phi(t+x)| \\ &\leq \|\phi(t+x)\|_{K,M,N} \\ &\leq C C_{t,N} e^{-\alpha t} \|\phi\|_{K,M,N} \end{aligned}$$

In the similar way, we can prove the above inequality for $\Phi^{(k)}(t)$

Hence, $\Phi(t) \in \mathfrak{W}$

Now, let $f(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$ and $\Phi(t) \in \mathfrak{W}$ Therefore the action of $f(t)$ on $\Phi(t)$ defined by $\langle f(t), \Phi(t) \rangle$ is well defined. Since $f(t)$ and $g(t)$ are in \mathfrak{W}' therefore both are linear, also we know that convolution product preserve linearity therefore $f * g$ is linear.

Let $\{\phi_j\}$ be a sequence of testing function in \mathfrak{W} converges to 0 in \mathfrak{W} , by continuity

of g and smoothness of translation we must get a sequence

$\{\phi_j\} = \{\langle g(x), \phi_j(t+x) \rangle\}$ which is also converges to 0 in \mathfrak{W} .

By continuity property of $f(t)$, we must have $\langle f * g, \phi_j \rangle = \langle f, \Phi_j \rangle \rightarrow 0$

Hence $f * g$ is continuous. Therefore, $f * g \in \mathfrak{W}'$. From equation (6), $\theta(t) \in \mathfrak{W}$ and for $t > 0, se^{-st} \in \mathfrak{W}$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} LC\{f * g\}(s) &= \langle f * g, se^{-st} \rangle \\ &= \langle f(x), \langle g(t), se^{-s(x+t)} \rangle \rangle \\ &= \langle f(x), e^{-sx} \langle g(t), se^{-st} \rangle \rangle \\ &= \langle f(x), e^{-sx} LC\{g(t)\} \rangle \\ &= LC\{g(t)\} \langle f(x), e^{-sx} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{s} LC\{g(t)\} \langle f(x), se^{-sx} \rangle \\ &= \frac{1}{s} LC\{g(t)\} LC\{f(t)\} \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we proved that

$$LC\{f * g\}(s) = \frac{1}{s} LC\{f(t)\} LC\{g(t)\} \quad (12)$$

This result indicates that the additional factor $\frac{1}{s}$ involved in the result of LC-transform of $f * g$ if we compared it with standard convolution theorem of the Laplace transform. \square

4.2 Examples

Now, we find LC-transform of some regular and some singular distributions in \mathfrak{W}' .

Example(1): Heaviside step function

$$H(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } t \geq 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } t < 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Clearly $H(t)$ is a function of exponential order, hence $H(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$

$$LC\{H(t)\} = \langle H(t), se^{-st} \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} 1 \cdot se^{-st} dt$$

For $Re(s) > 0$,

$$LC\{H(t)\} = 1 \quad (14)$$

Example(2): $f(t) = e^{at}$, where $a \in \mathbb{R}$

Clearly e^{at} is a function of exponential order a , so that $e^{at} \in \mathfrak{W}'$

$$LC\{e^{at}\} = \langle e^{at}, se^{-st} \rangle = \int_0^{\infty} e^{at} \cdot se^{-st} dt$$

For $Re(s) > a$, we must have

$$LC\{e^{at}\} = \frac{s}{s-a} \quad (15)$$

Example(3): $f(t) = t.H(t)$

Since $f(t) = t.H(t)$ is a function of an exponential order α , for any $\alpha > 0$, hence

$f(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$

$$\begin{aligned} LC\{f(t)\} &= \langle tH(t), se^{-st} \rangle \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} t \cdot s \cdot e^{-st} dt \\ &= s \left[t \left(\frac{e^{-st}}{-s} \right) - (1) \left(\frac{e^{-st}}{s^2} \right) \right]_0^{\infty} \end{aligned}$$

For $Re(s) > 0$,

$$LC\{f(t)\} = LC\{t.H(t)\} = \frac{1}{s} \quad (16)$$

Example(4): $f(t) = \sin(at)H(t)$

Since $H(t)$ is a function of an exponential order 0, hence $f(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$

$$\begin{aligned} LC\{f(t)\} &= \langle \sin(at)H(t), se^{-st} \rangle \\ &= \frac{as}{s^2 + a^2}, \text{ for } Re(s) > 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$LC\{\sin(at)H(t)\} = \frac{as}{s^2 + a^2} \quad (17)$$

Example(5): $f(t) = t^n H(t)$, where n is non negative integer.

Since $f(t)$ is a function of exponential order α , where $\alpha > 0$, hence $f(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$

$$\begin{aligned} LC\{f(t)\} &= \langle t^n H(t), se^{-st} \rangle \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} t^n s \cdot e^{-st} dt \end{aligned}$$

For $Re(s) > 0$, we must have

$$LC\{f(t)\} = \frac{n!}{s^{n+1}} \quad (18)$$

Now, let us find LC-transform of some singular distributions in \mathfrak{W}'

Example(6): The Dirac Delta distribution ($\delta(t)$). For $\phi \in \mathfrak{W}$, we must have

$$\langle \delta(t), \phi(t) \rangle = \phi(0) \quad (19)$$

Therefore,

$$LC\{\delta(t)\} = \langle \delta(t), se^{-st} \rangle = se^{-s(0)} = s \quad (20)$$

Example(7): The shifted Dirac -Delta $f(t) = \delta(t - a)$, where $a \geq 0$

Since, $\langle \delta(t - a), \phi(t) \rangle = \phi(a)$, therefore $\delta(t - a) \in \mathfrak{W}'$

$$LC\{\delta(t - a)\} = \langle \delta(t - a), se^{-st} \rangle = s.e^{-as} \quad (21)$$

Example(8): $f(t) = \delta'(t)$

Since $\langle \delta'(t), \phi(t) \rangle = -\phi'(0)$, therefore $\delta'(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$ by equation (9), we have

$LC\{f'(t)\} = s LC\{f(t)\}$ Using this fact ,we may get

$$LC\{\delta'(t)\} = sLC\{\delta(t)\} = s.s = s^2 \quad (22)$$

Example(9): $f(t) = \delta^{(n)}(t)$

Clearly, $\delta^{(n)}(t) \in \mathfrak{W}'$ and by equation (10), we must get

$$LC\{\delta^{(n)}(t)\} = s^n LC\{\delta(t)\} = s^n .s = s^{n+1} \quad (23)$$

5 Conclusion

The suggested distributional approach to the LC-transform on \mathfrak{W}' represents a significant theoretical advancement that generalizes the classical LC-transform to a much broader class of objects called distributions in \mathfrak{W}' . This approach provides rigor to previously heuristic operational calculus and it maintains computational discipline while expanding its applicability in pure as well as in applied mathematics. All the theorems and examples in this article presented the power and elegance of this approach, showing that the $\delta(t)$ can be handled with mathematical precision while yielding physically meaningful results. This generalized approach of LC-transform establish that generalized LC-transform is a robust tool in the modern mathematical treatment of linear dynamical systems and differential equations. This study suggest that similar approaches could be fruitful for other existing integral transforms on suitable distribution spaces.

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